

UKBOL Standard Operating Procedure: Lysate archiving with FluidX 96-decapper

Version 1, January 2026, Jordan Beasley

Equipment required:

- IntelliXcap FluidX 96-decapper
- FluidX 0.26ml external thread tubes, racked
- 96-channel pipette
- Sterile 200uL tips

Procedure:

1. Defrost and spin down plate containing lysate
2. Turn the IntelliXcap on, using the switch at the rear of the system.
3. Ensure that the correct cartridge, matching the target tubes, is inserted.
4. Place the rack of capped tubes on the tray
5. Press the Start button on the screen. The instrument confirms the height of the tubes. If the height scan is successful, the machine begins de-capping. NOTE: If the instrument detects that the tube rack is of a height different to that expected, it returns an error message. If required, you can stop the current process by pressing the E-Stop button on the top of the unit.
6. On completion, the de-capped tubes are returned via the tray.
7. Transfer all of lysate from the plate into the tubes using a multichannel pipette.
8. Place the rack of uncapped tubes back on the tray.
9. Press the Start button on the screen. The instrument scans and detects the correct height of the tubes and begins the recapping process.
10. On completion, the re-capped tubes are returned via the tray.
11. Scan the tubes and box using the NHM Biobank box scanner.
12. Export CSV of tube positions and associated barcodes.
13. Import tube codes into collection management system associated with specimen records.
14. Print labels with FluidX tube code and attach to voucher specimen.